

SUSTAINABLE COMPOSITES FROM RENEWABLE BIOCHAR AND ENGINEERING PLASTIC

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ABSTRACT

Carbonaceous materials including carbon black, carbon fibres, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and graphenes have been widely investigated as reinforcing materials in various types of polymer composites. Their addition to a polymer matrix offers not only the enhanced mechanical/ thermal properties but also provides many other functional features such as moisture resistance, electrical conductance, and gas barrier performance. Recently, biochar, one of the inexpensive carbonaceous materials obtained through the pyrolysis of various agriculture, forestry and clean municipal resources, receives great interest for composite application due to their renewable nature, cost effectiveness and their thermal stability. Melt process has been effectively employed for the fabrication of miscanthus based biochar filled nylon 6, an engineering plastic. The effect of biochar concentration on the tensile, flexural and impact properties of nylon 6- biochar composites has been investigated by employing universal testing machine and impact analyzer. The obtained results indicate that the enhancement of interfacial adhesion between biochar and polymer matrix is necessary for the improved materials performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbonaceous materials receive an extensive attention due to their structural and morphological diversity, which have been used for many applications [1-3]. One of the key applications involves in utilizing them as reinforcing material for polymer composites [4]. Hence, the demand for carbon reinforced plastics expands significantly. Traditionally, the above discussed carbonaceous materials have been produced from carbon rich hydrocarbons that are derived from non-renewable petroleum resources. Emerging challenges in utilizing petrobased precursors are their finite and depleting nature, and also some concern about greenhouse gas emission. In order to address these issues, extensive efforts have been made to explore various renewable carbon resources as the feedstock, which are environmental friendly, cost effective and abundance in nature. A wide range of renewable feedstock including, whole or part of the plants, seeds, oils and industrial coproducts have been widely used for the fabrication of carbon materials [5]. Carbonaceous materials with different morphological features and physiochemical properties like activated carbon, carbon nanotubes, fibres, spheres, quantum dots and graphene have been produced from many renewable resources [6-10]. The produced renewable carbons have also been used for many applications including electronics, biomedical imaging, catalysis, environmental remediation, polymer composites and the energy technologies [11, 12].

Among the various renewable carbons, biochar is also a carbonaceous material with the advantage of enhanced thermal stability. It has been generated as a coproduct during the pyrolysis of plant derived biomass as a carbon-rich solid residue relatively at lower temperature $>700\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, under lower oxygen environment [13, 14]. They have been extensively used for the purpose of soil enhancement, metal processing and energy production. It has also been considered as the potential carbon sink and enhances the carbon sequestration to address various issues related to global warming and climate change [15]. However, the engineering applications of biochar is significantly low and needs more exploration for their enhanced commercial value and to improve the biochar economics aiming towards a sustainable growth of the pyrolysis industries [16]. The unique characteristics of biochar that include higher surface area, porosity, and sorptive behaviors have made it a suitable material for many applications including metal removal, catalysis, energy storage and biocomposites [17]. Recently, biochar has been explored for the composite applications such as sustainable filler in epoxy, polyazomethine (PAM), polypropylene (PP), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), nitrile and styrene-butadiene rubber matrixes [18-24]. Our recent investigation on polyamide 6/biochar composite reveals the effect of biochar with different particle size on their rheological properties [25]. In polymer composites, particularly with melt processing techniques, biochar exhibits an excellent thermal stability and enables wider processing window. The composite application of biochar as reinforcement is still in their infancy and extensive research has to be devoted to bring more commercial benefits.

As the demand for biobased materials increases significantly, researchers from both industry and academia intend to formulate novel materials from renewable feedstock, which are expected to create new market opportunity. Biocomposites that are derived from the fully or mixed renewable origin not only can address the possible replacement for the 100% petrobased counterpart but also to provide some desired performance for various applications. Thus a wide range of research has been devoted for the fabrication of composite materials with natural fibres as reinforcement. The challenge is to incorporate the natural fibres into various engineering plastics like nylon with higher processing temperature, which causes the degradation of natural fibres. In this context, biochar, which is produced from natural fibre, is a suitable material for the fabrication of sustainable biocomposites from engineering plastics. Hence, the present work investigates the effective reinforcement of biochar in nylon 6 with higher melt processing temperature. The effect of biochar concentration on the mechanical properties has been investigated and reported.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Nylon 6 (Ultradid® 8020 HS) resin was procured from BASF corporation and the received pellets were dried in a hot air oven at $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a minimum of 6 hours prior to processing in a mini twin screw extruder. The biochar was prepared from the chopped *Miscanthus giganteus* fibre at an average pyrolysis temperature of $497\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ using the facility at Genesis Industries, Redondo Beach, California, USA. The obtained biochar was dried at $105\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a minimum of 72 hours for the complete removal of existing moisture. The biochar was crushed into smaller pieces using a mortar prior to process with polymer.

2.2 Processing of Polymer Composites

The nylon 6 - biochar composites were obtained by melt processing of dried resin with biochar using a MiniCTW Micro-Conical Twin Screw Compounder (twin-screw extruder integrated with injection molding system) from HAAKE™. The composites with different nylon-6/ biochar compositions were processed at $240\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 100 rpm, with a 120 second residence time. After the extrusion, the molten material was transferred into a preheated sample collector and injected into the mold at 230 bar injection pressure and hold for 15s prior to demolding. Figure 1 shows the schematic representation of nylon 6 - biochar composite processing.

2.3 Characterization

Tensile and flexural properties of the nylon 6 - biochar composites with different formulations were carried out respectively in accordance with the ASTM D638 (Type V) and ASTM D790 in Universal Testing Machine (UTM) model Instron 3382. The tensile samples of the nylon 6 - biochar composites were stressed at a rate of 1 mm/min and the flexural analysis was carried out by employing the speed of 1.4 mm/min. Impact properties were investigated through notched izod impact test employing the TMI 43-02 Monitor Impact Tester. Impact specimens with the notch depth of 4.0 mm have been used for the testing by adopting ASTM D256. All the characterizations have been performed for five samples and the mean value with standard deviation has been reported.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of melt processing of nylon 6- biochar composites through mini compounder and injection molder.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Tensile Properties

Tensile strength at yield, yield elongation and Young's modulus of the virgin nylon 6 and its composites with different biochar compositions are reported in Figure 2. It was observed that the addition 10 wt. % biochar to nylon 6 matrix reduces its tensile strength over 45%.

Figure 2: Tensile properties of nylon 6- biochar composites (A- nylon 6; B- 90% nylon 6 + 10% biochar; C- 85% nylon 6 + 15% biochar; D- 80% nylon 6 + 20% biochar; E- 75% nylon 6 + 25% biochar)

Further increasing biochar content to 15, 20 and 25 wt. % showed no significant impact on the tensile strength, when taking the standard deviation into consideration. The decreased tensile strength of the nylon 6 with the addition of biochar indicates the poor compatibility between polymer matrix and biochar surface. In addition to that structural and morphological features, such as larger particle size distribution and defective nature, of the biochar contributes in their property reduction. Similar trend has been observed for the % yield elongation of the nylon 6 and its composites. The observed higher standard deviation of the tensile strength could be explained due to the significant variations in the aspect ratio, size, shape and defectiveness (pores and voids) of biochar particles. As the biochar content in the polymer increases, the tensile modulus of the composite materials gradually increases.

3.2 Flexural Properties

Figure 3 shows the flexural strength and modulus of the nylon 6 and its composite materials. It has been observed that the addition of biochar into nylon 6 caused the reduction in their flexural strength about 22%. Adding more biochar into nylon 6 matrix further reduced the flexural strength by 29%. Loading the filler with irregular size and shape could cause the mobility limitation and the deformation of the matrix phase, which eventually caused the reduction in their flexural properties of both strength and modulus. The observed 10% increment in the modulus of nylon 6 filled with 20 and 25 % biochar loading was observed due to the effective deformability restriction by the accumulated biochar in the matrix phase. This could cause the enhanced stiffness of the composite materials. The challenge is to improve the biochar-nylon interfacial adhesion and hence the functionalization of biochar surface has been suggested for the enhanced mechanical properties.

Figure 3: Flexural properties of nylon 6- biochar composites.
(A- nylon 6; B- 90% nylon 6 + 10% biochar; C- 85% nylon 6 + 15% biochar;
D- 80% nylon 6 + 20% biochar; E- 75% nylon 6 + 25% biochar)

3.3 Impact Strength

The impact strength of the nylon 6- biochar composites with different biochar loading is shown in Figure 4. It has been observed that the increasing biochar content in the composite material results in decreasing their impact strength significantly. Addition of 15% biochar into nylon matrix caused the reduction of impact strength by 49%, which illustrate the poor compatibility between biochar surface and polymer matrix. In addition to that the observed structural and morphological features, such as wider size distribution and the defective structure played a vital role in the property reduction. Further increasing the biochar content to as 10, 15 and 20% in nylon matrix caused no significant effects in

their impact strength and remains stable with the standard deviation values. The observed larger standard deviation is caused due to the poor dispersion of biochar particles within the nylon matrix and the defective structural nature of biochar, which needs to be addressed in order to enhance their impact performance.

Figure 3: Impact properties of nylon 6- biochar composites.
(A- nylon 6; B- 90% nylon 6 + 10% biochar; C- 85% nylon 6 + 15% biochar;
D- 80% nylon 6 + 20% biochar; E- 75% nylon 6 + 25% biochar)

4 CONCLUSIONS

Nylon 6 – biochar composites have been melt processed employing mini compounder and their tensile, flexural and impact properties have been investigated. Tensile, flexural and impact strength of the composites decreased as the wt. % of biochar was increased. In opposition to these behaviours, the tensile and flexural modulus of the nylon 6 – biochar composites were increased with the increasing filler concentration from 10 to 25%. The observed reduction in the mechanical properties of the nylon 6- biochar composites was caused not only due to the poor interfacial adhesion between polymer matrix and biochar surface but also their defective structure. This could be addressed through the surface modification of biochar with suitable functional materials.

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